

Strategic Management Business Journal

<http://www.strategicmanagementbusinessjournal.com/index.php/SMBJ>

Strategic Management Business Journal is a forum for researchers in management science, especially in creating the effect of improving organizational performance both in the study of human resource management, financial management, and marketing management.

FOCUS & SCOPE

Strategic Management Business Journal publishes research that investigates the management of organizational management, in creating management strategies, applied management in the aspects of human resources, finance, and product marketing to increase organizational excellence. This journal is dedicated to original research, both theory, and measurement methods, where this journal has the scope to improve organizational performance.

Strategic Management Business Journal seeks to identify, test, and provide solutions for research, communication, and relevant theories about creating capabilities and organizational survival. In addition, this journal serves as a valuable link for intellectual information relating to the research focus:

- **Human Resource Management**
- **Financial management**
- **Marketing Management**
- **Management Business Strategy**
- **Entrepreneurship**
- **Industrial Psychology**
- **Organizational Behavior**

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Publication Frequency

Strategic Management Business Journal focuses on management, business, business strategy, organizational behavior, and human resource governance to improve organizational / company performance. This journal is accessible to academics and business professionals. This journal is published twice a year, in **June** and **December**.

Author Fee

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